

Civilizational choice of Ukraine

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Abstract

The article is concerned with the study of the project of civilizational development of Ukraine in the context of modern social and political changes. Noticed that civilizational choice of Ukraine especially acute at the stage of transition of world society to the post-industrial phase of its development. Underscored that the roots of the Ukrainian ethnos lead to the Trypillia civilization and simultaneously the Ukrainian local civilization has the features of a border civilization.

The conducted research allows determining the civilization project of Ukraine at the present stage, which in a new way actualizes the importance of science.

It is proposed to start developing the foundations of uniting the people of Ukraine on the basis of the Code of Ethics, which should be based on the consistent ethical imperatives of the Ukrainian people on the basis of common humanistic values.

Key words: civilizational development, civilizational project, civilizational choice, moral and ethical core.

Introduction

The urgency of the research topic is due to the fact that the issue of civilizational choice of Ukraine reached its apogee at the stage of transition of world society to the post-industrial phase of its development.

In the modern world, when the established international order is violated, the latest

technologies and communications are rapidly developing, economic and ethnocultural relations are globalized in the direction of becoming a holistic planetary civilization, each country makes its own choice of civilizational development.

Material and methods

Sufficient attention is now being paid to the issue of civilizational choice of states, particularly in Ukraine (Danyliak, 2019; Petrachkov, 2016; Pyrozhkov et al., 2016). Virtually all researchers who have followed this scientific discourse believe, that Ukraine was and is being a part of Europe and should join the European Union.

Meanwhile, these experts note that the people of Ukraine do not accept the path of European integration unanimously. Furthermore, scientific intelligence does not offer core ideas in the field of civilizational approach on the basis of which the people of

Ukraine can be united. It was this circumstance that gave impetus to write this article.

However, today the concept of civilization is relevant not only as a category of culture, but also as a category of wider comprehensive usage. Given the dynamics of civilizational integration of the world, most scholars adhere to civilizational typologies that do not significantly contradict the concept of A. Toynbee.

Consequently, today, the choice of civilization of Ukraine is still between the following models:

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1) Ukraine belongs to the Western civilization;

2) one part of it belongs to the Western civilization, the other – to the Eurasian civilization;

3) it is an original Eastern European subcivilization.

However, the data presented in the scientific works show that the readiness of Ukrainians to choose in favor of Europe, even at the level of declarations, is not unanimous, although the

share of those who are positive about it is constantly growing. At the same time, experts do not propose the civilizational principles of uniting the people of Ukraine to form a relative unanimity in the choice of civilizational path of development.

The purpose of the article is to highlight the key areas of implementation of the project of civilizational development of Ukraine and to propose the foundations of the civilizational basis for the unity of the Ukrainian people.

Results and discussion

The crisis of its civilizational self-identification has been going on in Ukraine for almost three decades.

Due to the processes of globalization, this crisis is typical for most modern countries, but in Ukraine it is felt most acutely against the background of transformations caused by the deep and prolonged recession of the world economy and the exhausting hybrid war of Russia.

We believe, that civilizational changes in modern countries, especially in polyethnic ones, should take place on the basis of social dialogue and consensus – they mean the civilizational choice made by the government, the elite and the people. This fully applies to Ukraine as well.

At the same time, it should be noted, that since Ukraine is not at the center of any of the civilizations, it cannot correspond to any of them. Therefore, it is logical to conclude that two civilizational identities although contradictory, but in reality, coexist in the society: The Euro-Atlantic and the Orthodox, the cores of which are North Atlantic (mostly Protestant) and Eurasian (Orthodox). At the same time, it is almost completely forgotten, that the roots of the Ukrainian ethnos are the Trypillia civilization.

We believe that the choice of civilization is the choice of lifestyle and values, that are effective for the development of the country. On this basis, the country chooses friends, partners, forms alliances, blocs, and so on. That is why the civilizational choice is a matrix of existence and a strategy the movement towards this direction (Pyrozhkov, Maiboroda, & Shaihorodskyi, Yu., 2016, p. 6).

It must be acknowledged, that the civilizational choice of a country cannot contradict with the

archetypes of culture and mentality of its population. However, the development of civilization constantly requires society to make a conscious choice of one or another way of integration. Thus, the civilizational choice of the country means not only the choice of its development, but also the formation of its civilizational project as a concentrate of views, which will define the way of life, interests and values as guidelines for the balance of human, society and state.

Modern results of public opinion polls indicate that the civilizational orientations of the Ukrainian people are diverse, and most of them are in a state of uncertainty. At the same time, “citizens are divided by their values, norms, traditions, guidelines into groups that form different cultural and civilizational types” (Pyrozhkov, Maiboroda, & Shaihorodskyi, Yu., 2016, p. 21).

A clear indicator of the public attitude to market relations and private property is its attitude to the land market, which shows how cultural codes affect the attitudes of the population in the material sphere. It is believed that often cultural and historical guidelines can be stronger than material arguments (Pyrozhkov, Maiboroda, & Shaihorodskyi, Yu., 2016, p. 24-25).

In addition, there is a large stratum of people in the country who have not yet formed certain values of civilization due to complex internal conflicts against the background of the transition from socialism to capitalism.

We believe that despite the fact that Ukraine is following the European path, it should be noted that the Ukrainian local civilization has the features of a border (adjacent) civilization. Such

civilizations are marked by an ambiguous, often conflicting intertwining of the parameters of their culture and neighboring cultural and historical types, between which the local civilization is. As a rule, it eventually becomes part of a larger civilization, but at the same time retains its borderline features for a long time.

In the countries of the frontier type civilizations, the following types of intercultural contacts can be distinguished.

Open confrontation, as the most primitive type of cultures interaction, when anything different is denied, although being constantly encountered. This type of interaction has a destructive potential for society. For example, the Ukrainian ethnos civilization was formed in the course of confrontation with the steppe peoples with Poland, Lithuania, Moscovia, Austria-Hungary, which at different times sought to absorb the indigenous Ukrainian culture. But such confrontation creates symbiotic cultural enclaves, social strata.

Interaction of cultures, that are relative and spiritually connected by religion, common ethnic origin, language, while each party remains independent and no new quality arises. This type of interaction is relatively stable. In some periods of civilizational synthesis, various components may prevail: cultural or religious value system, state, economic activity.

All frontier civilizations are characterized by incompleteness of their historical face. In particular, the remnants of subcivilizations, which included different parts of Ukraine-Russian, Austro-Hungarian, Polish – are still mixed in the modern Ukrainian ethnos.

Resulting interaction, when a qualitatively new phenomenon is born, is significantly different from the original participants of contact. Thus, classical civilizations are more characterized by synthesis, while borderline civilizations – by a complex interaction of symbiosis and synthesis.

It is believed that if the synthesis component wins in a frontier civilization, it evolves into the classical civilization; if the symbiotic component / prevails, then such a civilization-state is doomed to collapse.

That is why we believe, that in Ukraine it is important to support the synthesis processes of

socio-cultural and political development by all means – citizenship, mutual enrichment of cultures, religious and national tolerance, prevention of racial and interethnic confrontation, introduction of multilingualism and more.

Ukraine's productive civilizational choice means the creation of its civilizational project – the image of the future, which generates a strategy of worthy and effective realization in the world, in the process of which identity is combined with the progress of civilization. In other words, Ukraine's civilizational project is a model of its survival in the post-industrial world. That is, the civilization project of Ukraine is an ideal and desirable model of society. However, in order to make this model realistic, it is necessary to take into account the real-world development trends.

Ukraine's civilization project aims to build a mature civil democratic society. In order to do this, it is necessary to create conditions for dialogue between all forces of society, which will correspond to the civilizational development of Ukraine with the archetypes of culture and the mental characteristics of the people who live in it.

We agree and support the statement that “civilizational choice as a state development strategy can be realized only by consensus, not just a compromise of political parties and groups that are actively involved in public life and represent different social strata and cultural regions of the country” (Pyrozshkov, Maiboroda, & Shaihorodskiy, Yu., 2016, p. 8).

It should be noted that modern post-industrial civilization is a civilization of innovative information technologies in all spheres of human life, including worldviews. We believe, that the civilization project of Ukraine can take place only under the conditions of Ukrainians' outlook transformations, which will not take place as a result of manipulative propaganda.

We believe, that today among the most important tasks of Ukraine's civilizational development there are: overcoming poverty, reducing inequality and shifting the tax burden from low-income groups to the more affluent sections of society with control over strict observance of laws by all citizens without exception; creating fair conditions for all citizens to earn money; radically change tax policy

(Pyrozhkov, Maiboroda, & Shaihorodskiy, Yu., 2016, p. 236).

Civilizational development should be carried out with the view of the local mental specifics of the inhabitants of the regions and should also be consistent with the processes of decentralization.

The cornerstone of the country's civilizational development should be the deepening of democratic reforms, as well as overcoming resistance from the oligarchy and the bureaucracy, support for small and medium-sized businesses, affected by global force majeure. We fully support the statement that "A positive result of democratic reforms should be the renewal of existing and implementation of the latest norms of political culture" (Pyrozhkov, Maiboroda, & Shaihorodskiy, Yu., 2016, p. 236).

It is believed, that entering the global space of civilization is a worthy entry into the world economy. This can only be done by a competitive economy of the sixth technological mode. It is absolutely necessary to increase budget expenditures on innovation while increasing the level of general culture of society (Pyrozhkov, Maiboroda, & Shaihorodskiy, Yu., 2016, p. 279).

Since the people of Ukraine can be attributed to border civilizations, it is important to support the synthesis processes of civilizational development.

It should also be noted, that today, despite the fact that the majority of the Ukrainian population identifies itself as representatives of various Christianity branches, there are many representatives of other religions and those, who consider themselves non-believers.

Since the people of Ukraine are guided by different ethical principles, civilizational codes,

which are the core of religious or moral and ethical guidelines, we propose to begin developing a Code of Ethics for the people of Ukraine, which may be based on consistent ethical imperatives of traditional religions and moral and ethical guidelines of different nations, which make up the people of Ukraine.

Given the above, we believe that the Code of Ethics will be supra-confessional in nature and will be based on a harmonious combination of ethics, cultural and historical guidelines of different subethnic groups of the people of Ukraine in presiding over the values of the titular nation. In our opinion, such a program document should unite the people of Ukraine on the basis of tangible humanistic values.

The task of creating such a moral and ethical core of the civilization project of Ukraine at the present stage in a new way actualizes the importance of science. Based on the analysis of current global threats and challenges to our country, scientists are able to develop paradigms of civilizational reforms, as well as assess humanitarian dangers and risks along the way, generalizing strategies and scenarios for future development of Ukraine.

We believe that only thanks to this scientific approach, the civilization project of Ukraine will be a project of the civilization of humanistic innovations – the core of which should be the Code of Ethics of the people of Ukraine. It's slogan should be: "The only ethics – a cohesive state". The implementation of such a project according to a science-based approach is a fundamental condition for ensuring national security and the very existence of Ukraine as an independent state.

Conclusions

Thus, the article highlights the key ways for implementation of Ukraine's civilizational development project, which mainly affect the socio-humanitarian sphere, including the outlook.

It is proposed to start developing the worldview foundations of uniting the people of Ukraine on the basis of the Code of Ethics of the People of Ukraine, which should be based on the consistent ethical imperatives of traditional

religions and moral and ethical guidelines of the Ukrainian people on the basis of common humanistic values.

Prospects for further research

Development of a model of the Code of Ethics of Ukraine taking into account the civilization codes of the nations that make up the people of Ukraine is a vital issue for future research.

References

- Danyliak O. (2019). Tsyvilizatsiyni vybir Ukrainy teper zakriplenyi v Konstytutsii [Civilizational choice of Ukraine is now enshrined in the Constitution]. *NISS*. Retrieved May 25, 2020 from: <https://niss.gov.ua/news/komentari-ekspertiv/civilizaciyniy-vibir-ukraini-teper-zakriplenyi-v-konstitucii-0>.
- Petrachkov A. (2016). Try tsyvilizatsiini proekty i maibutnie Ukrainy [Three civilization projects and the future of Ukraine]. *Nezalezhnyi kulturolohichni chasopys*. Retrieved May 25, 2020 from: http://www.ji-magazine.lviv.ua/2016/Petrachkov_Try_civilizacijni_proekty.htm [in Ukrainian].
- Pyrozhkov, S., & Khamitov, N. (2016). Tsyvilizatsiyni vybir Ukrainy v hlobalizovanomu sviti [Civilizational choice of Ukraine in a globalized world]. *Dzerkalo Tyzhnia*. Retrieved May 25, 2020 from: <https://zn.ua/ukr/internal/civilizaciyniy-vibir-ukrayini-v-globalizovanomu-sviti-yakiy-civilizaciyniy-vibir-robot-ukrayinu-ne-ob-yektom-a-sub-yektom-geopolitik-.html> [in Ukrainian].
- Pyrozhkov, S., Maiboroda, O., Shaihorodskyi, Yu. et al. (2016) *Tsyvilizatsiyni vybir Ukrainy: paradyhma osmyslennia i stratehiia dii: natsionalna dopovid* [Civilization choice of Ukraine: the paradigm of understanding and strategy of action: a national report]. IPIEND im. I. F. Kurasa NAN Ukrainy [I.F. Kuras Institute of Political and Ethnic Studies of the National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine]. Kyiv, K.: NAN Ukrainy. 284 p. [in Ukrainian].